

MODERN SLAVIC PEOPLES DURING GLOBALIZATION

Abdurakhimova Shahzoda Ravshanbek kizi

Student of the Faculty of Philology and Language Teaching
Fergana State University

Isayeva Zera Tairovna

Teacher of the Faculty of Philology and Language Teaching
Fergana State University.
Fergana, Uzbekistan.

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Abstract. This paper examines the complex interaction of modern Slavic peoples with globalization processes. It examines how global trends influence the preservation and transformation of the cultural, linguistic and national identity of the Slavs in the context of intensive migration flows, economic integration and information exchange. The paper examines both positive and negative aspects of globalization for the Slavic world, such as opportunities for economic growth and cultural exchange, as well as the risks of losing national identity and increasing social inequality. The study uses comparative analysis methods, statistical data and case studies of individual Slavic countries, which allows for a comprehensive understanding of the role and place of the Slavic peoples in the modern globalized world.

Key words: geopolitics, globalization, integration, modernization, Slavic world, civilization.

The world civilization of the early 21st century is a socio-economic, technological and cultural organism, where the global problems facing humanity morally, socially and economically determine the need to develop alternative trajectories of the historical path of civilization, reorient all types of human activity, radically change the worldview, go beyond the boundaries of technocratically oriented values and ideals, "the socio-historical and cultural prerequisites for the emergence of ideas of a Slavic orientation arose in the lands of the Western Slavs, this was associated with the national liberation movement, one of the main elements of which was the idea of the need for unity and mutual assistance of the Slavic peoples» [1,c.28]. In Russia, interest in this movement arose after the Napoleonic wars among the Russian intelligentsia.

The ideas of Slavism were actualized and played an important role in solving geopolitical problems over the following centuries: in 1941 they became the basis for the organization of the All-Slavic Committee to mobilize the struggle of the Slavic peoples against fascist Germany: in 1946 the All-Slavic Council was held with the participation of representatives of the Slavic peoples;

in 2005 the IX All-Slavic Congress announced the creation of the Union State of Belarus and Russia, which can be seen as a signal for the restoration of a multipolar world.

The Scientific and Educational Center of North Caucasian Slavic Studies of the Kuban State University has been studying the history of the Slavic world for a number of years: Russian-Ukrainian relations; historical and ethnocultural choice of the Slavic peoples; Byzantium, Ottoman, Austro-Hungarian and German empires in the fate of the southern and western Slavs; cultural heritage of the Slavic peoples; globalization and the Slavic world, etc. "Kuban scientists have accumulated certain theoretical and empirical material on the conceptualization of the phenomenon of "Slavism", the study of the essence, content and dynamics of this image in the context of historical problems, interethnic communications and the assessment of the influence on the processes of image transmission in the international arena.

Despite the importance of the issue under study, literary sources do not contain a clear definition of the categories of "Slavism" and "Slavic world", there is a range of judgments and opinions, which is associated with a large set of concepts that these images carry.

For a social formation that is part of the global evolutionary process, the law of divergence is true - the plurality and complexity of civilizations existing in continuous competition, mutual enrichment and complementation: archaic, less capable of adapting to changing conditions and innovations are displaced by viable ones that meet the conditions of the habitat - as a result, synthesis and mutual penetration occur. Each civilizational formation is a complex evolving system, within which there is a continuous interaction of various competing forms: production, spiritual and cultural, some elements are replacing others.

Along with the variability of civilizational characteristics, there are conservative ones that determine the features of an ethnic group in time and space and build possible schemes and trends of historical development. The wheel of history of the Slavic world was influenced by natural, climatic, geographical and geopolitical factors. The special position between the East and the West determined the cultural diversity of the Slavic peoples, the emergence of geocultural phenomena.

Такого рода геокультурные образования относятся к категории «пограничных»: целостные общности, сформировавшиеся на границах крупных цивилизационных образований на протяжении длительного

времени и в результате синтеза близкородственных и генетически отдаленных культур.

Such formations are characterized by such features as polyethnicity, tolerance, religious tolerance, the ability to culturally adapt to the achievements and values of other cultures. These categories fully apply to the Slavs and the Slavic world as a whole.

The weak point of border geocultural formations is the incompleteness of the unrealized cultural synthesis, which makes these formations permanently transitional, contradictory and unpredictable, they are especially sensitive in the competitive struggle of civilizations.

Can the global problems of our time be considered as a threat to the Slavic world, bearing in mind the events in Yugoslavia and Ukraine? Globalism and its negative consequences cannot be associated with the 20th century. The prerequisites for globalization were laid throughout the history of mankind. Over the past centuries, the peoples of the world have been solving two problems: achieving national sovereignty and independence, freedom from external oppression and establishing democratic control over their own power, subordinating it to constitutional and legal norms.

An authoritative specialist on the issue we are studying, A.S. Panarin, notes that the greatest illusion is that the process of global modernization is carried out in line with a single universal perspective. The inclusion of less developed countries in the single standard of developed countries is collapsing in the course of this process. According to M.G. Delyagin, "globalization is the process of forming a single global financial information space based on new, primarily computer technologies, which qualitatively changes the nature of business." [2, p.65] This trend fundamentally changes the nature of cooperation between developed and developing countries. The creative development of the latter by the former with the help of direct investment gives way to destructive development by withdrawing financial and intellectual resources. The gap between rich and poor countries based on the operation of such a system will not decrease, but rapidly increase.

Politically, globalization does not lead to integration, but to monopolization, to the formation of a unipolar world, with the center of this new world order being the financial capital of a number of developed countries under the auspices of the United States of America. The authors of globalization do not stop only at financial and economic manipulations. They are well aware that the most effective business is the transformation of human consciousness.

"Traditionally, it was believed that the main subject of labor was the change of nature, now it is the impact on human consciousness» [3, c.40].

The various types and forms of technologies and advertising, unlike traditional marketing, do not adapt the product to people's preferences, but, on the contrary, people to the product. Technologies for manipulating people's consciousness and behavior through various forms of propaganda, belittling national and cultural traditions, and imposing foreign social norms and values have been intensively developed. "Industrial civilization, having generated a powerful scientific and technical base, implementing the phenomenon of economic globalization. In its spiritual and value orientations, it remained at the level of primitive ideas of a mass consumer society» [4,c.13].

Geoculture as a method has unique capabilities and abilities in understanding and preserving images and traditions in interpreting historical images in its local space, it acts simultaneously as a process and as a result of development, which allows us to consider it as a tool for influencing the socio-cultural space.

Despite the obviousness of geoculture as a method of semantic definition of this phenomenon, there is no, which gives rise to variability of positions, quite heterogeneous. Situations arise when an object carries a double semantic load. On the one hand, it represents a structural component of physical geography, on the other - the sphere of material activity, a set of cultural images synthesized from various natural, social, material and ideal elements that form a specific civilizational space.

Thus, geoculture takes the form of branding of territories, entering and going beyond their civilizational boundaries; such subjects can be peoples that are not part of the core of a particular civilization, including those belonging to civilizational pimitrophs.

The problems of globalization, economic, political and cultural disproportions complicate the possibilities of constructing a modern geocultural space of the Slavic world without its unification. In the axnological dimension, geoculture represents a field in which various schemes are concentrated that influence each other, including the dynamics of space. Spatial schemes have a certain semantic charge, contributing to the formation of a "force field" that affects nearby areas of civilizational space. Geoculture in this capacity is perceived as a system of regulatory bases for activity and its sign-symbolic content.

A.S. Kolesnikov in his book "Philosophical Comparative Studies East - West" attempted to present the history of slavians as one of the specific areas of the historical and philosophical direction. Geoculture can contain, in addition to the economic structure, a system of social relationships between members of society, production, distribution, a set of basic ideological attitudes - all components of this complex are interconnected, interact and form a single civilizational space.

The first project of globalization can be considered the Hellenistic culture with the characteristic features of universalism, which formed the basis of Western European civilization. The conquest of Western Asia and Central Asia by Alexander the Great led to the creation of the Hellenistic world. Greek culture, which was basically inclined to universalism, had to become common to the whole world and interact with other cultures. The Roman Empire repeated the cultural processes of the Hellenistic world: it absorbed the Hellenistic and created a global culture; brought its principles of morality, law, political consciousness to Western culture, creating a unified state-legal organization; its characteristic features. Thanks to the Roman civilization, the medieval West was born, the Hellenistic civilization did not disappear, although its development as an organic chain ended. Hellenism is a unique phenomenon that gave general cultural values in all areas of spiritual and material human activity.

The Byzantine world has its own characteristics: Greco-Roman and Eastern traditions left their mark on public life, statehood, religion, philosophy and culture. The Byzantine world, while different from the East and the West, is at the same time a link between the two worlds. The Byzantine world had a profound influence on the countries of medieval Europe, the area of distribution of which is from Southern Italy and Sicily to the Balkan Peninsula, Crimea and the Caucasus.

The West and the East spread their ideology, culture, religion, and way of life on a global scale. Rome embraced almost all European countries with its influence. In the Balkan Peninsula and further north, beyond the lower reaches of the Danube, as well as in the countries between the Black and Baltic Seas, where the Russian state was formed, the Byzantine civilization was restored. The peoples who entered the arena of the world historical process were distributed among global entities.

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